

On the Specific Heat of Liquids

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Prof. Honda¹ proposed a formula for the specific heat of liquids on the basis of rotational energy of the molecule, but Prof. Lindemann² showed that the rotational energy cannot account for the large specific heat of liquids. The author in the present note, proposes an empirical formula for the energy of the liquid per unit mass.

$$E = 3NkT + \frac{N}{2} \frac{x}{(e^x - 1)} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where $x = \frac{h\nu_1}{kT}$, and N the number of atoms per unit mass. and ν is given by Lindemann's well known formula³

$$\nu_1 = 2.08 \times 10^{11} \left[\frac{T_1}{mV^{\frac{2}{3}}} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

T is the absolute temperature, h and k are Planck's and Boltzman's constants.

From (1) C_v is found to be

$$C_v = 3Nk + \frac{Nk}{2} \frac{e^x x^2}{(e^x - 1)^2} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Table (1) gives a few values calculated from (3) and for comparison C_p is given in the last column [Landolt and Bornstein tables].

TABLE I.

Liq.	Abs. Temp.	$\gamma \times 10^{12}$	C_p Cal.	C_p
Cl	200	2.24	.20	.22
Br	270	1.70	.08	.107
Hg	240	1.25	.032	.033
Sn	510	2.24	.059	.064
Bi	610	1.6	.037	.036
Pb	610	1.8	.032	.040
Al	970	7.5	.27	.39
Cs	299	.95	.053	.058
K	335	2.3	.18	.22
Cu	1357	6.7	.12	.15
Li	460	1.0	1.0	1.3
Na	396	3.96	.31	.33
Ag	1300	4.36	.065	.074
Zn	700	4.36	.11	.12

The calculated values are in general less than the experimental values of C_p . Since $C_p - C_v = T\alpha^2/\rho k$ where α is the volume expansion, k the compressibility, and ρ the density, C_v could be computed from the experimental values C_p , but no data seem to be available for compressibility. k for liquids is of the order of 10^{-12} per dyne, hence $C_p - C_v$ is not greater 10^{-2} . Therefore it is believed that the calculated values are fairly close to the true value.

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¹ Phil. Mag., January, 1923.

² Phil. Mag., June, 1923.

³ Phys. Zeits., 1910, p. 689.